

On the Integration of Approximate Computing in GNSS Signal Processing for Improved Energy-Efficiency

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Abstract—Continuous miniaturization of GNSS receivers has led to reduction of energy consumption over the years. Yet, these remain one of the highest energy consuming sensors in embedded electronics, rendering their integration difficult in platforms with high energy-constraints. In parallel, the developments of novel computation paradigms, such as Approximate Computing, have opened new possibilities to further reduce the receiver energy consumption by trading-off computation accuracy. In this paper, we analyze the application of AxC operators inside the GNSS processing chain. More precisely, we apply various AxC multipliers inside the correlation operations used for signal tracking and look at the impact on the post-correlation SNR values. We show that the degradation in SNR values can be low, depending on each AxC multipliers implementation, thus offering significant energy saving opportunities in correlators.

Index Terms—Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), Global Positioning System (GPS), Approximate Computing (AxC), Digital Signal Processing (DSP), Digital Arithmetic

I. INTRODUCTION

Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) is a key technology used by billions of devices today [1]. Its free global access and accurate positioning capacity make it a must-have for any device requiring outdoor positioning. General improvements in modern electronics have led to a continuous miniaturization of the GNSS receivers, leading to the concept of “low-power GNSS” and their integration into energy-constrained embedded devices. However, GNSS receivers remain high-energy consuming sensors [2]. This can complicate their integration into the newest Internet of Things (IoT) platforms with limited size and strict energy consumption constraints (e.g., wildlife tracking). New processing methods are needed to meet these new energy constraints.

Recently, a novel paradigm called Approximate Computing (AxC) has emerged, identifying trade-offs between acceptable computational accuracy and energy consumption. While optimizations in algorithms, software and hardware has always been a part of the electronic designs, AxC goes beyond a simple optimization, by intentionally providing inexact results, but still within an accepted precision for the targeted application. Releasing the constraints on having perfect computations

allows reductions in the energy consumption on the device in return.

Historically, AxC concepts have been applied at different system levels [3]: circuit level, such as voltage-overscaling [4] or approximate memory/logic [5]; arithmetic level, such as approximate arithmetic operands [6]; algorithm level, such as loop-perforation or transprecision typing [7]. The integration level is also related to the amount of modification needed in the system. For instance, voltage-overscaling might not require any software modification, while algorithm modification would require diving into the system behaviors for more successful implementation. While AxC techniques at any level can all offer large energy savings, their integration in a system requires an review of their impact on the computations and the precision required by the application.

Amongst all AxC techniques, approximate operators (e.g., adders, multipliers) are promising due to the minimum code changes needed for their integration. These operators have a simplified hardware logic compared to their exact counterparts, leading to potential errors in arithmetic operations, but also to savings in the hardware side, delays and power consumption. Many implementations of AxC operators have been presented over the recent years, and a comprehensive survey can be found in [3].

The use of AxC operators have been largely applied to image processing and AI/ML applications [8]. Nevertheless, some studies have also looked into applying them into the Digital Signal Processing (DSP) of wireless communication signals. In [9], the authors replaced the arithmetic unit of the pulse shaping and the matched filter of a 6G communication system, obtaining 87% dynamic power savings with a low impact on the Bit Error Rate (BER). In [10], the authors proposed a new design for a floating-point multiplier for 5G communication system, resulting in 65% of power saving with minimal effect of 0.2dB loss on the BER. Nevertheless, to the best of the Authors’ knowledge, no study have looked into the integration of AxC techniques inside the GNSS receiver processing, which is the aim of our paper.

In this paper, we review the integration of AxC operators within the GNSS DSP side. Ultimately, our goal is to lower the energy consumption of a GNSS receiver from the software side, finding the optimal point between the energy consumption and the satisfaction of the application’s

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Fig. 1. 2x2-bit unsigned multiplier logic, exact logic (left) and approximated logic (right) [6]

positioning requirement. In a previous study [11], we provided an overview of factors influencing the energy consumption of GNSS receiver. We highlighted that the energy consumption in the DSP side of the receiver (i.e., after ADC) is almost entirely taken by the acquisition and tracking phase. While FFTs can be used during the acquisition of signal, effectively lowering its complexity [11], the complexity of the tracking phase is dictated by the correlation operation. In this paper, we propose an AxC correlator concept by replacing the multiplier operator used inside the correlation operation by an approximated version. Multiple AxC multipliers are tested and the impact of the post-correlation SNR is reviewed. We summarize our contributions as follow:

- C1** Review of AxC operators for GNSS AxC correlators;
- C2** Implementation of a simulation framework to evaluate the AxC operators impact on GNSS signal processing;

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Approximate operators

The main concept of an AxC operator is to approximate the logic circuit implemented in an exact operator, which leads to inaccurate mathematical operations, but also to savings in hardware area, circuit delay, and power consumption. These inaccurate operations can introduce errors, and their rate and magnitude depend on the approximate operator design. Many architectures of approximate arithmetic can be found for each arithmetic operation. Each of these architectures leads to differences in logic gate area, circuit delay, and power savings, as well as different error magnitude, spreading, and probability. Determining if the errors are under the acceptable threshold for the envisioned application is necessary for selecting the optimal AxC arithmetic. We remark that the errors related to AxC arithmetic are not random; those are deterministically based on the value combination. Therefore, predicting an operator's error will be related to the probability of a specific number of combinations happening.

Taking the example of a simple two-bit unsigned multiplier, developed in [6] and represented in Fig. 1. By definition, an unsigned n -bit integer can represent up to 2^{n-1} numbers. Multiplying two n -bit numbers yields a maximum result of $2n$ bit numbers. In our case, a two-bit number can represent four numbers, namely $[0, 1, 2, 3]$, thus, the maximum value possible is 9. When looking at the values of these apparent numbers, it becomes clear that the operation $3 \cdot 3 = 9$ is the only operation using the first bit in the binary representation, thus needing 4 bits to be stored. In contrast, other operations only need 3 bits to store their result. Consequently, the multiplier circuit can be greatly simplified by allowing this operation to be represented by the maximum value possible using 3 bits (i.e., $111 = 7$). The Error Magnitude (EM) is $9 - 7 = 2$, with an Error Magnitude (EM) of $1/16$. In [6], an area usage reduction and power saving of 10-40% is presented, depending on the operating frequency.

In our paper, we used the AxC operators developed in the EvoApproxLib [12]. Multiple signed/unsigned adders and multipliers for 8 to 16 bits integers are defined in the library, obtained through genetic programming to maximize specific parameters such as delay, area, or power. Conventional architecture designs (i.e., Ripple-Carry Array, multiple Carry-Save Array, Wallace Tree) are provided as initial seeds to perform the optimization. In this work, we focused on the 8-bits signed multiplication operations, thus reviewing the nine AxC operators defined in the EvoApproxLib: 1KV6 (i.e. exact), 1KVM, 1KXF, 1L12, 1KV8, 1KV9, 1KVP, 1KVQ, 1KX5 and 1KVA. Unfortunately, it is unclear how each proposed approximation relates to the initial seeding. Moreover, while three additional AxC operators are available (i.e., 1L2J, 1L2L, 1L2N), they were discarded from this analysis as highlighted has not working properly in the Github repository of the library.

In Fig. 2, we represented the power consumption w.r.t. the mean average error, as reported inside the library [12]. The power consumption of the addition operation can be reduced almost 10 times, when comparing the highest and lowest energy consuming implementations (i.e. 1KV8 and 1L12). The advantage of using the EvoApproxLib is its open-access and easy integration in high-level language, such as

Fig. 2. Power consumption of AxC multipliers from the EvoApproxLib w.r.t. Mean Average Error from the exact multiplier (1KV6) [12]

Python. Yet, since the operators developed are only available in 8/12/16 bits integer types, it limited our simulation to high quantization signals. Nevertheless, it allowed us to perform software simulations of the impact of AxC operators, further developed in Section III.

B. Approximate correlators

A bottleneck in the complexity of acquisition and tracking algorithms is related to the correlation operation [11]. When split into basic operations, a correlation is comprised of the multiplication and summation of the elements of two signals, as described in the correlation mathematical expression:

$$C = \sum_{n=1}^N S_1[n] \cdot S_2[n], \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of samples, n is the sample index, S_1 and S_2 are the two signals to be correlated, and C is the result of the correlation.

We note that the correlation operation defined in Equation (1) is equivalent to a Multiply-and-Accumulate (MAC) operation. Approximate MAC operators have been proposed in previous research [13], [14]. In this paper, we are not exploring these implementations and instead we propose a custom approximate MAC function, designed by simply replacing the multiplication operation with an approximated one. The choice of replacing only the multiplication operations comes from two reasons: (1) Multipliers are known to be more energy consuming than adders, especially for integer operations [12]; (2) In a MAC operator, the total sum grows gradually, and the adder operation require thus more bits to operate, contrary to the multiplication operation that remains fixed in size, thus easier to model in our simulations.

Approximate operators are defined with different error metrics, the most important being the magnitude and rate.

However, the value of the error is deterministic, as it depends on the values of the input numbers. This characteristic is important, as given the distribution of numbers that will be computed, the errors are predictable and quantified and do not need to be modeled into a random error distribution model (e.g., normal distribution). Let ϵ_m be the error of an approximate multiplication operation. Applied to Equation 1, we obtain:

$$\tilde{C} = \sum_{n=1}^N S_1[n] \cdot S_2[n] + \epsilon_m. \quad (2)$$

where \tilde{C} is the approximated correlation results.

It comes naturally that a small error happening at every summation might result in a very large error in the final correlation C . Yet, this should only be the case if the error ϵ_m is biased, i.e., non-zero centered. As the correlation might involve thousands of summation operations, it is likely that the error is compensated if the error induced by the approximate operator has a normal distribution. The effects of the approximate operator bias is reviewed further in Section III.

III. SIMULATIONS CAMPAIGN

Simulations were conducted to evaluate the effect of various AxC operators on the correlation operations. More specifically, we focused on the impact on the post-correlation SNR, looking for potential SNR degradation due to the errors induced by the AxC operators. To perform the analysis, we generated artificial GPS L1 C/A signals and perform the correlation with exact and approximate multipliers. As the sampling frequency and Carrier-to-Noise Ratio (CN0) are known to have an impact on the post-correlation SNR, we performed a parametric simulation of these parameters in our simulations, to isolate the effect related only to AxC operators. Moreover, we added different level of noise inside the artificial signals to simulate more realistic conditions, and performed Monte Carlo simulations within our parametric simulation. The generation of the signals was performed in several steps and is described in the following section.

A. Signal simulation

In this paper, we focus only on GPS L1 C/A signals. We assume the correlation is performed on a perfectly synchronised signal, with no code shift, Doppler effect or intermediate frequency. This allows us to simplify the signal model to only the PRN code. This was assessed sufficient to get an initial evaluation of the effect of AxC operator on the correlation operation. The signal is then up-sampled to the required sampling frequency.

An Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) is added on top of the signal, to replicate the noisy aspect of the correlation. The noise is randomly generated, based on Standard Deviation (StD) parameter retrieved from the targeted C/N0. The relation between CN0 and the noise StD is described in the following equations [15]:

$$SNR_{dB} = C/N0_{dB} - BW_{dB}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_n = \sqrt{10^{(S_{dB} - SNR_{dB})/10}}, \quad (4)$$

where BW_{dB} is the bandwidth in dB, taken as twice the sampling frequency in our simulations; S_{dB} is the signal power in dB; σ_n is the noise standard deviation.

The obtained signal is quantized to a number of signed integer steps, according to the quantization chosen, assuming an ideal Automatic Gain Control (AGC). Note that it is necessary to encode the quantization into integers to adequately review the impact of the AxC operators tested. As described in Section II, the distribution of the values are important in the definition of the error linked to the AxC operator. Quantization was limited to 8 bits, as the library used for AxC operators only provide 8/16 bits implementations. While this can be seen as very high quantization for GNSS signals, which can use up to 1-bit quantization for low-power GNSS cases, it can still have realistic application for high-sensitivity receiver, as signals with high-quantization are known to be more resistant to interferences [16].

To remove the effect of the random number generation introduced by the noise, the simulation of the signal is reproduced 1,000 times in Monte Carlo simulations, for each combination of sampling frequency / CN0. For this simulations, we tested sampling frequencies ranging from 2.046 to 20.46 MHz and CN0 ranging from 20 to 55 dB.

B. Simulation results

The noisy quantized signal is correlated with the original PRN code. Correlation is performed with the nine signed 8×8 AxC multipliers available in the EvoApproxLib. Only partial correlation is performed over a limited area around the main correlation peak. It allows reduction of the processing time, and is sufficient to obtain an estimation of the post-correlation SNR. Note that depending on the each AxC, a bias might be present in the correlation results. This was corrected by removing the mean noise value from the correlation results.

The post-correlation SNR is computed according to equation 5, comparing the ratio between the correlation central peak and the average noise outside the central peak [17]:

$$SNR_{PC} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } N > P \\ \frac{P-N}{N} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where P is the correlation at the peak and N is the average correlation noise outside the peak.

In Fig. 3, we provide the post-correlation SNR values w.r.t the C/N_0 and the AxC operator used (as defined in the EvoApproxLib [12]). The average difference in SNR from the exact multiplier is also provided in dB. The standard deviation ($1 - \sigma$) is estimated from all the Monte Carlo runs and the different sampling frequency tested.

Overall, while there is a strong correlation between C/N_0 and post-correlation SNR values, we can see significant differences between the various tested AxC implementations. Certain AxC operators, such as 1KV8 and 1KVP, show reduced post-correlation SNR on average. Other operators, such as AxC 1KVM and 1KXF, show almost the same results as the

Fig. 3. Mean post-correlation SNR for 8-bits multipliers w.r.t. C/N_0 using different AxC operators

exact operator. The most interesting results is from the AxC 1L12, with very limited losses compared to the exact operator, but of all operators tested, it is the one with the highest errors. Moreover, 1L12 is the least power consuming operator of all the 8×8 signed operators implemented in the EvoApproxLib. This clearly highlights the potential of approximate operators, that can result in very minimum losses in correlation while providing huge energy savings. It also supports our interests in performing simulations on a wide range of approximate implementations, to find optimal trade-offs between power saving and computation quality.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we provided an overview of the impact of AxC operators on correlation results for GNSS signal tracking. In total, nine AxC multipliers were tested, leading to low-to-high error magnitude in the computations. Interestingly, the AxC multiplier with the highest mean average error (i.e., 1L12) also provided results very close to the exact multiplier, with limited degradation to the post correlation SNR. This supports our hypothesis that the AxC operators can be used within correlation operations to drastically reduce the energy consumption of the tracking phase.

Future research will look into the impact on the Auto-Correlation Function (ACF) shape, in the presence of Doppler and code shifts as well as of multipaths, in order to understand if the AxC correlators might induce additional delay errors. Similarly, the simulations should be extended to lower signal quantization, and would require the development of additional inexact arithmetic unit functions. The impact on the tracking loop robustness should also be assessed, potentially mixing exact and approximate operation to maintain the tracking loop accuracy within the user requirements. Finally, testing on real signals and other GNSS signal types (e.g. Binary Offset Carrier (BOC)) should also be performed in future research.

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